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High-temperature radiation resistance of NiCoFe medium-entropy alloy enabled by stable nanostructures and defect evolution mechanisms

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ABSTRACT

The study innovatively examined a nano oxide dispersion-strengthened (ODS) NiCoFe medium-entropy alloy with nanosized grains to address the challenge of discovering structural materials for high-temperature irradiation applications, such as in advanced nuclear reactors. The ODS-NiCoFe alloy exhibited a nanoindentation hardness of 4.3 ± 0.9 GPa, representing a two-fold enhancement over the 2.0 ± 0.1 GPa of single-crystal NiCoFe. Dislocations were identified as the primary defect structures. Following irradiation (Ni^{2+} , 580 °C), the average dislocation length density increased from $\sim 2.6 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$ to $\sim 6.1 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$, while the mean dislocation length decreased from 249 nm to 104 nm, contributing to a relative irradiation hardening of 25 %. Additionally, the study demonstrated the stability of various nanostructures, with only minor changes in the average sizes of nanoprecipitates and grains—from 6.7 ± 1.7 nm to 6.4 ± 1.7 nm, and from 73 ± 2 nm to 76 ± 2 nm, respectively, upon irradiation, suggesting effective defect annihilation at interfaces and grain boundaries. The alloy exhibited no observable irradiation-induced voids. Molecular dynamics simulations revealed irradiation resistance of the alloy through the absorption of vacancy clusters at grain boundaries and Shockley-dominant-dislocation chains and the absorption of interstitial clusters at grain boundaries, aided by the high mobility and three-dimensional motion of interstitial clusters. Thus, the findings demonstrate the high-temperature radiation resistance of the novel ODS-NiCoFe alloy, surpassing that of well-known ODS steels, using a correlative approach that combines experiments and simulations.

1. Introduction

The development of structural materials for advanced nuclear reactor designs such as Gen IV, which operate under extreme service

conditions, including temperatures exceeding 500 °C, radiation damage above 50 displacements per atom (dpa), corrosive environments, and high-structural stresses, has been an active area of research for several decades [1–3]. In the past decade, there has been a surge in the

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development of complex concentrated alloys (CCAs) for such potential structural material applications [4–6]. Concentrated solid solution alloys (CSAs) are a unique group of CCAs. CSAs are typically single-phase (SP), such as body-centered cubic (bcc), hexagonal close-packed, or face-centered cubic (fcc) structures [5]. CSAs contain multiple principal elements, often in nearly equal atomic percentages. Even when elements are present in non-equiatom proportions, their concentrations are still sufficient to enable significant interactions among the transition metals (TMs). The variation of TMs leads to different levels of chemical disorder, sometimes tunable [5]. In the past years, different categories of SP-CSAs, such as high-entropy alloys with five or more principal elements and medium-entropy alloys (MEAs) with generally three principal elements, have been of great interest [4,5,7]. The alloys possess multi-functional properties such as high thermal stability, corrosion resistance [8], hardness [9], fatigue and wear resistance, high strength-to-weight ratio, and high-temperature strength, which are tunable depending on the alloy combination [10–14]. CSAs exhibit higher atomic-level stresses and are chemically complex [15,16]. It is also suggested that the dissipation of energy deposited by irradiation in CSAs can be modified by choosing the number, type, and concentration of alloying TMs [5]. Hence, CSAs show better radiation damage resistance than conventional alloys, with lower swelling [17], better phase stability, irradiation defect formation resistance, and minimal irradiation hardening [6].

Alternatively, oxide dispersion-strengthened (ODS) steels, primarily containing Y_2O_3 particles and Y–Ti–O clusters, have been developed, which show superior radiation resistance and mechanical properties [18,19], as the particles/precipitate interfaces can act as defect sinks and facilitate strengthening via dislocation pinning. In addition, grain refinement to obtain a few nanometer-sized grains, compared to conventional coarse-grained alloys, has demonstrated great promise, as the grain boundaries can act as defect sinks and provide dislocation pile-up strengthening [20,21]. Thus, such strategies have proved valuable for potential usage in advanced nuclear reactor materials. In some recent studies, strategies such as oxide dispersion strengthening with nanoscale precipitates and nanoscale grains were combined and applied to CSAs, to obtain a novel family of alloys, which can be called ODS-CSAs [22–27]. ODS-CSAs can solve all the major issues encountered by structural components in advanced nuclear reactors and hence, it is essential to design, characterize, and evaluate such alloys. However, only limited investigations have been conducted for a general understanding and specifically for the radiation damage response of these alloys [22–27]. Hence, ODS-CSAs require significant attention in the context of developing new materials for advanced reactor concepts. The current research attempts to address this partly by examining one of the potential candidates, ODS-NiCoFe, for high-temperature irradiation effects.

In a previous study, molecular dynamics simulations demonstrated that the NiCoFe alloy exhibits a higher defect recombination rate than pure Ni, due to reduced energy dissipation via atomic displacements, which allows for a longer recombination time [28]. Hence, the NiCoFe CSA showed better high-temperature irradiation-swelling resistance compared to other similar CSAs such as NiCo, NiCoCr, NiFe, and NiCoCrFe [28]; however, it possesses poor mechanical properties, with a yield strength of 559 MPa and a hardness of 232 ± 5 HV [23]. Consequently, novel ODS-NiCoFe is a favorable strategy to improve the mechanical properties and further enhance the high-temperature radiation swelling resistance. In the limited literature available, ODS-NiCoFe has shown grain refinement and superior mechanical properties compared to NiCoFe [23,24]. ODS-NiCoFe ($2Ti_2Y_2O_3$) exhibited an average grain size of 237 nm, as opposed to 735 nm with no oxide particles [24]. The ODS-NiCoFe alloy also demonstrated high compressive strengths of 1295 MPa and 127 MPa at room temperature and 700 °C, respectively, due to the presence of sub-micron-sized grains and nano-oxide particles [24]. In a similar study, ODS-NiCoFe ($1.5Y_2O_3$) and ODS-NiCoFe ($1.2Ti_1.5Y_2O_3$) showed grain refinement, with average grain sizes of

483 ± 172 nm and 456 ± 187 nm, respectively, compared to 854 ± 480 nm in NiCoFe [23]. Also, the texture component changed from γ -fiber to α -fiber during hot rolling for NiCoFe, while the changes were suppressed with the additions of Y_2O_3 and Ti + Y_2O_3 [23]. Additionally, ODS-NiCoFe ($1.5Y_2O_3$) and ODS-NiCoFe ($1.2Ti_1.5Y_2O_3$) exhibited yield strengths of 981 MPa and 1050 MPa, respectively, in contrast to NiCoFe with 559 MPa, indicating strengthening due to grain refinement and the presence of nanosized oxide particles [23].

The refined grains and improved mechanical properties even at high temperatures obtained with the addition of nanosized oxide particles in NiCoFe are encouraging. However, the effects of high-temperature irradiation on the mechanical behavior and the microstructural evolution of the novel ODS-NiCoFe require exploration. Hence, the current state-of-the-art research aims to investigate some of the major effects of irradiation such as the stability/instability of nanostructures (oxide nanoprecipitates and grains), irradiation hardening, and irradiation swelling in the recently developed ODS-NiCoFe at high temperature. In this research, we utilized various experimental techniques such as nanoindentation, transmission electron microscopy (TEM) techniques, and X-ray diffraction (XRD), following Ni^{2+} irradiation at 580 °C. We employed molecular dynamics (MD) overlapping cascade simulations to complement the experimental results. Overlapping cascade simulations have been widely used to understand radiation damage in metals and alloys [30–39]. The short simulation time in MD simulations leads to a dose rate several orders of magnitude higher than that in experimental conditions. However, previous studies employing similar overlapping cascade approaches to simulate damage accumulation in metals and multicomponent alloys have demonstrated good agreement with experimental observations [30,31,37,38]. Even at higher temperatures, such simulations can qualitatively describe the experimental results for multicomponent alloys [39]. Specifically, in Ni-based multicomponent alloys, large vacancy clusters are almost immobile compared to pure Ni, and their behavior can be captured in MD simulations without being overly sensitive to the differences in dose rates. Additionally, it is well-known that beyond a certain dose threshold, the behavior of the materials becomes dominated by defect clusters and dislocations [40], which are less sensitive to dose rate variations. Therefore, overlapping cascade simulations remain a valuable tool for understanding the mechanisms of irradiation damage in multicomponent alloys, even at high temperatures, despite the inherent limitations of the high dose rate. The experimental and MD simulation studies established the high-temperature irradiation-swelling resistance and relative irradiation-hardening resistance of the unique ODS-NiCoFe alloy.

2. Experimental

2.1. Sample preparation and ion-irradiation

The ODS-NiCoFe (NiCoFe - 1.2 wt% Ti - 1.5 wt% (Y_2O_3 + ZrO_2)) alloy was synthesized through mechanical alloying (MA), spark plasma sintering (SPS), and annealing. Additionally, the single-crystalline fcc single-phase equiatom NiCoFe was produced via arc melting, drop casting, and optical floating zone melting, for comparison. The alloys, ODS-NiCoFe and NiCoFe, were manufactured at the University of Tennessee, Knoxville (UTK), USA, with detailed information in Guo et al. [23,24]. To facilitate material characterization, the samples were cut with dimensions of approximately 5 mm × 5 mm × 2 mm and then polished to a mirror finish. Subsequently, specific regions of the specimens were irradiated with Ni^{2+} ions at 580 °C using TEM grids at the Ion Beam Materials Laboratory, UTK [41], as outlined in Jin et al. [29]. The Ni^{2+} ion irradiation utilized an energy of 3 MeV and a fluence of 5×10^{16} ions/cm² [41] with the corresponding irradiation damage and Ni^{2+} concentration depth profile detailed in Fig. S1 (Supplementary Information). The Stopping and Range of Ions in Matter (SRIM) program [42] was employed for these calculations using the full-damage cascade calculation option with a target density of 8.553 g/cm³. A threshold

displacement energy of 40 eV was utilized for Ni, Co, and Fe, which was deduced from the ASTM standard [43]. Also, the SRIM calculations employed lattice binding energies of 5.9 eV, 4.6 eV, and 5.8 eV, for Ni, Co, and Fe, respectively, as suggested by Agarwal et al. [44]. The final cut-off energy was also chosen to be 40 eV (same as the threshold displacement energy) in the SRIM calculations instead of the default 1 eV to circumvent the vacancy over-estimation [45]. Furthermore, the VACANCY.TXT method was used for the dpa calculation [45]. The calculations revealed a Ni²⁺ concentration maximum of ~1.04 % at ~1.08 μm with a peak damage of ~103 dpa at ~0.86 μm. The range of PKA energies obtained via SRIM calculations could vary between less than 1 keV and up to 2300 keV for 3 MeV Ni²⁺ irradiation. Fig. S2 shows the abridged plot of the frequency distribution of the PKA energies. The frequency distribution of the PKA energies indicated that ~80 % of the values are <1 keV and ~96 % of the values are <10 keV.

2.2. Characterization

2.2.1. Nanoindentation

The NanoTest Vantage system (platform 3) was utilized to perform nanoindentation on the NiCoFe and ODS-NiCoFe samples to assess hardness locally at irradiated and pristine regions using a Berkovich indenter. To probe the hardness from the irradiated region only (approximately 1.6 μm from the surface – Supplementary Information, Fig. S1), the research team used the most conservative approach of collecting the data from the depth equivalent to about 10 % of the irradiation depth. To assess the specific load to meet this criterion, a series of indents using loads of 1 mN–10 mN were performed. The corresponding hardness values at various depths and loads are shown in Fig. S3. As a result, the indentations with a 2 mN load in pristine and ion-irradiated samples were utilized to assess irradiation hardening. Thus, a maximum load of 2 mN ensured that the indentation-induced plastic deformation zone remained within the irradiated region of the samples. For the pristine region of the NiCoFe alloy, as shown in Fig. S3, a minimal indentation size effect (ISE) was observed and at a depth exceeding 300 nm, the ISE was negligible. To further minimize ISE, the Diamond Area Function of the indenter for a 2 mN load and a polynomial describing the shape of the indenter were calculated [46] at the corresponding depth in all analyses. In addition, both pristine and ion-irradiated samples were assumed to be burdened with similar ISE even though it was minimal. Hold times of 1.2 s and 2.2 s were employed at the maximum load for the irradiated and pristine regions, respectively. Multiple nanoindentation measurements were conducted and the average hardness values were calculated to ensure the values were statistically representative. The team measured the hardness values by calculating the projected area of the indentation (A_p) and using the relationship, $H = P_{\max}/A_p$, where P_{\max} is 2 mN in the current studies.

2.2.2. Electron microscopy and related techniques

2.2.2.1. Preparation of TEM lamellae. The research team employed a dual-beam scanning electron microscopy/focused ion beam Helios 5 UX (Thermo Fisher Scientific) microscope, equipped with EasyLift™, to perform the lift-out and prepare electron-transparent lamellae from the irradiated regions of the ODS-NiCoFe sample for TEM microstructural studies. A protective layer of carbon was deposited on the lamellae, and cuts were made with a depth of at least ~4 μm, enabling the examination of both the irradiated (top 1.6 μm - Supplementary Information, Fig. S1) and pristine regions. To minimize the impact of Ga⁺ ions on the microstructure, the team gradually reduced the beam acceleration voltage to 2 kV during the thinning of the lamellae. Several TEM techniques and instruments were then utilized to investigate various microstructural features in the lamellae.

2.2.2.2. TEM and Scanning(S)TEM imaging. The FEG JEOL JEM-F200

and FEI Talos™ F200X FEG (S)TEM microscopes, operated at 200 kV, were employed to identify defect microstructures in the irradiated and pristine regions of the lamellae via TEM and STEM bright-field (BF) imaging. In ODS-NiCoFe, the lamellae were tilted to reveal dislocations in various grains. The team calculated the thickness of the lamellae by using convergent beam electron diffraction patterns and calculated dislocation densities by utilizing the line-intercept method [47]. The mean dislocation lengths (d_{mean}) were then obtained by using the relation, $d_{\text{mean}} = (\rho_{L,\text{Total}} \times V) / N_{\text{Disc}}$, where $\rho_{L,\text{Total}}$ is total dislocation length density of the grains examined, V is volume of the examined region, and N_{Disc} is number of dislocations in the examined region.

2.2.2.3. Nanoprecipitate characterization. A cold FEG, probe- and image-spherical aberration-corrected, JEOL ARM 200CF microscope, operated at 200 kV, was utilized to conduct STEM-low-angle annular dark-field (LAADF), STEM-electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS), and high-resolution (HR) TEM in the irradiated and pristine regions of ODS-NiCoFe. To analyze the nanoprecipitates, the STEM-LAADF images were examined, and the nanoprecipitate density and sizes were calculated using the ImageJ software [48]. The team assessed the physical stability of the nanoprecipitates by comparing irradiated and pristine regions. The STEM-EELS technique was utilized to determine the thickness of the regions of interest from the lamellae, facilitating nanoprecipitate density calculations. The research group also used STEM-EELS to deduce the chemical distribution of the elements to identify radiation-induced segregation (RIS) in the precipitates and HR-TEM to identify radiation-induced loss of crystallinity in the precipitates.

2.2.2.4. Orientation mapping with scanning precession electron diffraction (SPED)-ASTAR. A JEOL 2100F microscope equipped with a SPED setup was used to conduct orientation mapping via ASTAR in the irradiated and pristine regions of ODS-NiCoFe. We utilized a spot size of 3.7 nm and a scan size of 320 x 600 pixels. The team indexed the diffraction data for the matrix phase, NiCoFe, and Y₂Ti₂O₇ precipitate phase and carried out the orientation mapping using NanoMegas ASTAR [49]. This is one of the earliest endeavors demonstrating such a new avenue for the microstructural characterization of irradiated materials. The orientation maps were further analyzed using the MTEX MATLAB software [50] to evaluate grain size, misorientation distribution, and grain orientation spread in the grains, providing insights into the physical stability of the nano-sized grains.

2.2.3. XRD analysis

For XRD analysis, the Bruker AXS D8 Advance diffractometer, equipped with a sealed Cu X-Ray tube, TWIN-TWIN optics, and a LYNXEYE XE-T strip detector, was employed. The analysis was performed in Bragg-Brentano (BB) and grazing incidence diffraction (GID) configurations. In the GID configuration, a parallel beam was directed at the sample with a 3.5° incidence angle, ensuring that 95 % of the diffraction signal collected by the detector originated from the top ~1 μm of thickness. This configuration facilitated the analysis of the irradiated region. Conversely, in the BB configuration with a divergent beam, the X-ray penetration was deeper, revealing the pristine state of the sample. The Bruker DIFFRAC.EVA program with the database of diffraction standards ICDD PDF4+2022 [51] and the DIFFRAC.TOPAS programs were applied for phase identification and to refine the models that describe the obtained diffraction patterns for the phases identified. The crystal lattice constant was obtained via the Nelson-Riley extrapolation [52]. The fundamental parameters profile fitting in TOPAS for BB configuration and via the measurement of a standard reference material, LaB₆, for GID configuration, were used to assess the instrumental contribution towards the peak broadening. The team used the TOPAS program to model the peak broadening contributions for the peaks corresponding to the <111> and all the others separately. The D. Balzar

double-Voigt approach [53] simplified to pure Lorentzian and Gaussian analytical functions representing the size- and strain-broadening, respectively, were applied. The Williamson-Hall plot [54] justified the assignment of the common local lattice strain parameter to all peaks.

3. Computational models and methods

In this study, MD overlapping cascade simulations were used to understand the mechanisms of nucleation, migration, and aggregation of vacancy and interstitial clusters in single-crystal and bicrystal (with a grain boundary) NiCoFe CSA. These simulations were conducted using the large-scale atomic/molecular massively parallel simulator, LAMMPS [55]. The second nearest-neighbor modified embedded-atom method (2NN MEAM) potential, developed by Choi et al. [56], represented the atomic interactions in NiCoFe. This potential has proven effective in recent MD investigations related to defect evolution [57,58], thermodynamic properties [59], and plastic deformation in the NiCo-based MEAs [60–63]. The parameters of the 2NN MEAM potential were adjusted for unary Co based on Do et al. [57] to capture short-range interactions accurately.

A single-crystal of pure Ni was initially constructed, comprising 269,824 atoms with dimensions of $110.49 \text{ \AA} \times 242.36 \text{ \AA} \times 114.05 \text{ \AA}$ along the $\langle 100 \rangle$, $\langle 010 \rangle$, and $\langle 001 \rangle$ directions, respectively. Subsequently, Ni atoms were randomly substituted with Co or Fe atoms until the desired equal molar composition (Ni:Co:Fe = 1:1:1) was achieved. Periodic boundary conditions were applied in all three directions. After reaching molecular statics minimization, the system was equilibrated at the target temperature (580 °C) and zero pressure using the NPT ensemble for 100 ps. To simulate an irradiation event, a recoil energy of 5 keV was imparted to the central atom in a random direction, leading to a collision cascade throughout the system. This energy maintains a balance between capturing essential cascade dynamics and computational feasibility. This energy level has been widely used in other studies to predict radiation damage in fcc metals and alloys [30,32–35,37–39]. Also, the 5 keV-PKA energy used for MD simulations is a reasonable choice to qualitatively correlate with the experimental results, as the PKA energy distribution calculated via SRIM calculations compares well, as represented in Fig. S2. To prevent excessive heating, the border regions of the sample cells (4 \AA slabs on each side of the cell) were cooled down to the target temperature using a Berendsen thermostat [64] for 50 ps following the initial recoil. Similarly, the entire cell was maintained at 580 °C using the Berendsen thermostat for an additional 20 ps, while controlling the pressure in the system with a Berendsen barostat [64]. The irradiation events were repeated 480 times in all cells, representing ~ 0.11 dpa according to the Kinchin-Pease approximation, i.e., $dpa_{Kp} = (n/N) \times (E_{recoil}/2E_d)$, where n denotes the number of cascades, N represents the total number of atoms in the box, E_{recoil} refers to the energy of the recoiled atom, and E_d signifies the displacement threshold energy [65]. We utilized a displacement threshold energy of 40 eV in the simulations. To efficiently capture essential irradiation behavior and saturate defective atom counts, MD simulations were limited to ~ 0.11 dpa, given the computational expense of high-dose cascade simulations [11]. Following each irradiation event, we randomly shifted the cell in all dimensions across the periodic boundaries to ensure homogeneous irradiation throughout the system.

To evaluate the effect of grain boundaries (GBs) on the formation, movement, and aggregation of defect clusters, a $\Sigma 5$ (210) high-angle symmetric tilt GB with a misorientation value of 53.1° was selected. The $\Sigma 5$ (210) grain boundary (GB) was constructed by joining two perfect crystals along the (210) plane. The X, Y, and Z axes of one of the crystals were oriented along $[021]$, $[0 \bar{1}2]$, and $[100]$, respectively, while the other crystal was oriented along $[0 2\bar{1}]$, $[012]$, and $[100]$. During the joining process, the atoms that overlapped within a specified cutoff distance (0.04 \AA) from the boundary were removed to determine the most stable structure with the lowest potential energy. The research

team chose the size of the simulation box to closely match that of the single-crystal. After minimizing the system, the dimensions of the box were $111.57 \text{ \AA} \times 242.61 \text{ \AA} \times 114.05 \text{ \AA}$, containing 273,280 atoms. Due to periodic boundary conditions, multiple GBs occur in the simulation cell with a separation of approximately 121.26 \AA . The research team applied the same cascade simulation, originally used for the single-crystal, to the bicrystal. To ensure the reliability and statistical significance of the results, cascade simulations were performed on three samples for single-crystal NiCoFe and three samples for bicrystal NiCoFe.

To analyze the vacancy concentration for the MD simulations of single-crystal and bicrystal NiCoFe, the Wigner-Seitz cell method was employed [66,67]. For extracting the vacancy and interstitial cluster distributions, the research group performed a cluster analysis (CA) considering a cut-off value equal to the mean of the second and third nearest neighbors of the atoms. The identification of defective atoms was carried out using the Adaptive Common Neighbor Analysis (a-CNA) [68]. To study the evolution of dislocations during cascade simulations, the Dislocation Extraction Algorithm (DXA) [69] was utilized. The CA, a-CNA, and DXA were performed using the OVITO software [70].

To comprehend the effects of irradiation within nanoprecipitates, cascade simulations were conducted using a methodology similar to the one employed for NiCoFe. The simulations were performed for up to 200 events in pyrochlore $Y_2Ti_2O_7$, as a representative model oxide nanoprecipitate. The simulation box contained 88,000 atoms with dimensions of $10b \times 10b \times 10b$, where 'b' represents the lattice parameter. For modeling atomic interactions, a classical pair potential, as described by M. Dholakia et al. [71], was employed. This interatomic potential includes the Buckingham-type pair potential [72], coupled with the Coulomb potential, making it suitable for highly energetic processes [71, 73]. The coordination numbers of Ti atoms in $Y_2Ti_2O_7$ precipitates during the cascade simulations were analyzed using the OVITO software [70].

4. Results

4.1. Nanoindentation hardness and irradiation hardening

Fig. 1 shows the effect of the presence of nanostructures such as the nano-sized grains and nanoprecipitates formed due to the addition of nanoparticles (Y_2O_3 and Ti) and irradiation, on the mechanical behavior of NiCoFe. As shown in Fig. 1 (a)–(d) in the form of example load-displacement (LD) curves corresponding to approximately average nanoindentation hardness values, NiCoFe and ODS-NiCoFe show irradiation hardening, indicated by shallower indentation depths for the irradiated region relative to the pristine region. For instance, in these particular LD curves, the maximum indentation depths reduced from 197 nm to 177 nm (Fig. 1 (b)), and from 128 nm to 118 nm (Fig. 1 (d)), with irradiation for NiCoFe and ODS-NiCoFe, respectively. Fig. 1 (b) and (d) also demonstrates creep of the materials at the maximum load of 2 mN, by 15 nm and 7 nm for the pristine and irradiated regions of NiCoFe, respectively, and 3 nm for pristine and irradiated regions of ODS-NiCoFe. The average creep depth values at the maximum load of 2 mN were 7 nm and 10 nm for the pristine and irradiated regions of NiCoFe, respectively, and 4 nm for pristine and irradiated regions of ODS-NiCoFe. Thus, the pristine region of NiCoFe creeps to a greater depth denoting weaker mechanical strength, as revealed by certain previous studies, which indicate a low yield strength of 559 MPa and a microhardness of $232 \pm 5 \text{ HV}$ for NiCoFe [23,24].

Fig. 1 (e) exhibits a column chart of average hardness values, indicating an enhancement in the pristine regions from $2.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ GPa}$ for NiCoFe to $4.3 \pm 0.9 \text{ GPa}$ for ODS-NiCoFe, demonstrating nanoprecipitate dispersion and grain boundary hardening. Such a more than twofold increase in hardness is significant, considering the poor mechanical properties of NiCoFe [23,24]. Thus, the hardness of pristine ODS-NiCoFe is comparable to or even greater than that of various ODS steel alloys reported in the literature [74–77]. In addition, Fig. 1 (e)

Fig. 1. Variation of nanoindentation hardness with irradiation and the presence of nanostructures (nanoprecipitates + nano-sized grains). (a) Example load-displacement (LD) curves for single-crystal NiCoFe from pristine and irradiated regions. (b) Enlarged section of the LD curves, shown in (a), near maximum load. (c) Example LD curves for polycrystalline ODS-NiCoFe from pristine and irradiated regions. (d) Enlarged section of the LD curves, shown in (c), near the maximum load. (e) Column chart of hardness for NiCoFe and ODS-NiCoFe from pristine and irradiated regions.

indicates an increase in hardness from 2.0 ± 0.1 GPa to 2.5 ± 0.3 GPa for NiCoFe and from 4.3 ± 0.9 GPa to 5.4 ± 1.1 GPa for ODS-NiCoFe, following irradiation. The estimated relative increase in hardness due to irradiation was approximately 25 % for NiCoFe and ODS-NiCoFe, serving as a measure of irradiation-induced hardening.

4.2. STEM-LAADF characterization of the nanoprecipitates

Fig. 2 (a), (b), and (c) depicts the STEM-LAADF images demonstrating the presence and distribution of nanoprecipitates (dark contrast) in irradiated and pristine regions of ODS-NiCoFe. The nanoprecipitate distribution appears homogeneous across the sample,

although the size distribution varies. Fig. 2 (b) and (c) shows 167 and 157 nanoprecipitates in irradiated and pristine regions, respectively. The corresponding nanoprecipitate densities are $9.27 \times 10^{22} \text{ m}^{-3}$ and $9.02 \times 10^{22} \text{ m}^{-3}$, indicating that the densities are similar in irradiated and pristine regions of ODS-NiCoFe. The equivalent diameter distribution of nanoprecipitates, illustrated in Fig. 2 (d), closely follows a lognormal distribution (see inset), characterized by a typical long tail. This wide range of nanoprecipitate sizes helps explain the large standard deviations observed in the nanohardness values of ODS-NiCoFe (Fig. 1 (e)), as local precipitate size influences the indentation response. The average (geometric mean) equivalent diameters of the nanoprecipitates are 6.7 ± 1.7 nm and 6.4 ± 1.7 nm in the irradiated (Fig. 2 (b)) and

Fig. 2. Distribution of oxide nanoprecipitates. (a)–(c) STEM-LAADF images depicting the presence of oxide nanoprecipitates in ODS-NiCoFe sample (a) including irradiated and pristine regions with irradiation profile overlaid, (b) irradiated region, and (c) pristine region. (d) Equivalent diameter distribution of the oxide nanoprecipitates for irradiated and pristine regions of ODS-NiCoFe and representative lognormal distributions (inset). STEM: Scanning transmission electron microscopy, LAADF: Low-angle annular dark-field.

pristine (Fig. 2 (c)) regions, respectively. The difference in average nanoprecipitate sizes between pristine and irradiated regions is statistically insignificant, as confirmed by a two-sample hypothesis *t*-test (Supplementary Information – Tables S1 and S2). The equivalent diameters of the nanoprecipitates from the pristine regions of the sample

are not accurately representative, as the pristine region was also under the influence of temperature during irradiation.

Fig. 3. Chemical and crystallinity changes in oxide nanoprecipitates. (a)–(d) STEM-EELS images depicting the distribution of Y, Ti, Zr, and O in the irradiated region of ODS-NiCoFe. (e) Compositional profile along the grey rectangle shown in (b). (f), (g) High-resolution TEM images of the two largest precipitates identified in STEM-EELS. (h), (i) Fast Fourier transforms (FFT) of the region of loss of crystallinity and crystalline region, respectively, of the precipitate observed in (g). (j) Molecular dynamics overlapping cascade simulation analysis showing the variation of the percentage of Ti atoms with coordination number (CN) above and below six in Ti–O bonds with the increase of the number of cascade simulations. STEM: Scanning transmission electron microscopy, EELS: Electron energy loss spectroscopy.

4.3. STEM-EELS and HR-TEM evaluation and molecular dynamics overlapping cascade simulation of the nanoprecipitates

Fig. 3 (a)–(d) shows the elemental mapping of Y, Ti, Zr, and O in the irradiated region of ODS-NiCoFe, corresponding to the same area depicted in Fig. 2 (b), obtained by using STEM-EELS. We used Y, Ti, Zr, and O maps to reveal oxide nanoprecipitates. In ODS-NiCoFe, we identified two types of oxide nanoprecipitates, Type I and II, as indicated in Fig. 3 (b), similar to a previous work [24]. Type I precipitates are primarily Ti-Oxides with smaller amounts of Y and Zr, while Type II precipitates are Y–Ti–Zr-Oxides containing similar amounts of Y, Ti, and Zr. The upper left corner of Fig. 3 (a)–(d) also shows the possibility of the occurrence of a mixed-type precipitate. Fig. 3 (e) shows the compositional profile along the longer edge of the grey rectangle, with atomic percentages of each element integrated along the shorter edge. Fig. 3 (e) divulges that some regions of Type II precipitates undergo chemical

segregation, indicating Ti enrichment with a simultaneous depletion of Y and Zr along with a slight enrichment of matrix elements, Ni, Co, and Fe, due to irradiation. Fig. 3 (f) and (g) (high-resolution TEM images) and the corresponding Fast Fourier transforms, Fig. 3(h) and (i), further inform us that the regions of chemical segregation remain crystalline, while other regions undergo loss of crystallinity irrespective of the type of precipitates. Fig. S4 illustrates the diffraction patterns obtained via SPED-ASTAR, which also indicates the possibility of the loss of crystallinity; even though the patterns show spots representing a crystalline phase. However, the nanoprecipitates do not show a significant loss of crystallinity in the pristine region, as shown in Fig. S5. The STEM-EELS data was also utilized to understand the carbon contamination due to ion-irradiation in the samples, as shown in Fig. S6. The compositional maps show negligible formation of carbides (for example, the blue circle in Fig. S6 (c)). Fig. 3 (j) illustrates the analysis of MD overlapping cascade simulations conducted on the model representative oxide,

Fig. 4. SPED-ASTAR analysis of polycrystalline ODS-NiCoFe. (a), (b) Grain equivalent diameter distribution with superimposed lognormal distribution (inset) for pristine and irradiated regions. (c), (d) Correlated and uncorrelated (inset) misorientation angle distributions with Mackenzie distributions overlaid (dotted curve - inset) for pristine and irradiated regions. (e), (f) Grain orientation spread distributions for pristine and irradiated regions. SPED: Scanning precession electron diffraction.

$Y_2Ti_2O_7$, which depicts that the irradiation affects the local short range order around the Ti atoms. Fig. 3 (j) indicates that the coordination around the Ti atoms decreases and hence, the number of Ti atoms with coordination below the standard defect-free coordination number of 6 increases with irradiation. The MD overlapping cascade simulations also revealed the loss of crystallinity after 200 cascades.

4.4. SPED-ASTAR analysis of the grain characteristics

Fig. S7 in Supplementary Information shows the inverse pole figure orientation maps of the pristine and irradiated regions. For the same scan size, the irradiated region contained 346 grains while the pristine region contained 369 grains, indicating a similar number of grains. Fig. 4 (a) and (b) illustrates the grain equivalent diameter distribution of the grains identified in Fig. S7 (a) and (b), respectively. The lognormal distributions shown in Fig. 4 (a) and (b) (see inset) describe the distributions. The average (geometric mean) grain equivalent diameters are 73 ± 2 nm and 76 ± 2 nm for pristine and irradiated regions, respectively. The equivalent diameters of the grains from the pristine regions of the sample are not entirely representative, as the irradiation temperature could affect the grain sizes. However, the difference in average grain sizes between pristine and irradiated regions is statistically insignificant, which is justified by a two-sample hypothesis *t*-test (Supplementary Information – Tables S3 and S4).

Fig. 4 (c) and (d) represents the correlated and uncorrelated (inset) misorientation angle distributions of the pristine and irradiated regions, respectively. The correlated data represent the misorientations calculated between the grains and their nearest neighbors, while uncorrelated data represent the misorientations measured between each scan point and all other points [78]. The Mackenzie misorientation angle distribution [79,80] which signifies a random orientation distribution is also superimposed on the uncorrelated misorientation angle distribution. Both irradiated and pristine regions follow approximately Mackenzie-type-misorientation angle distribution indicating that the orientations are randomly distributed and not significantly textured. The correlated distributions illustrate that mostly low-angle grain boundaries surround each grain as denoted by the peaks at misorientations less than 5° (Fig. 4 (c) and (d)), indicating sub-grains. The second highest peak in correlated distributions is observed at 60° , exhibiting the occurrence of annealing twins with $\Sigma 3$ ($\langle 111 \rangle$ 60°) boundaries. It is evident that the misorientation angle characteristics largely remain the same, post-irradiation, as shown in Fig. 4 (d). Hence, grain boundary migration during irradiation was minimal, validating the grain size stability shown in Fig. 4 (a) and (b). Fig. 4 (e) and (f) depicts the grain orientation spread (GOS) [78,81] (in degrees), which is calculated as a difference between the orientation of a scan point and

average grain orientation. The GOS can be used as a measure of plastic strain, as they are linearly related [81]. In the current work, irradiation-induced defects generated the plastic strain. As illustrated in Fig. 4 (e) and (f), the irradiated region indicates higher GOS, and the average GOS values were 0.6° and 0.53° for irradiated and pristine regions, respectively.

4.5. XRD characterization

Fig. 5 shows the normalized XRD patterns for ODS-NiCoFe indicating the fcc crystal structure (space group - $Fm\bar{3}m$) of the major phase, NiCoFe, using Bragg-Brentano (offset by 1 arbitrary unit of normalized intensity) and grazing incidence modes for pristine and irradiated regions, respectively. The NiCoFe phase shows no significant changes in lattice parameters following high-temperature (580°C) irradiation (Supplementary Information – Table S5). Fig. 5 (b) illustrates the broadening of the peak corresponding to $\{111\}$ following irradiation. The doublets observed in the data extracted from the pristine region, as shown in Fig. 5 (b), were due to the peaks related to $K\alpha_1$ and $K\alpha_2$ transitions; however, such doublets were not observed in the case of irradiated data because of the peak broadening indicating irradiation-induced defects. After accounting for instrumental broadening contributions, we calculated other broadening contributors such as the crystallite sizes and microstrains, and reported them in Table S5. The volume-weighted crystallite sizes, represented in Table S5, in the irradiated and pristine zones of ODS-NiCoFe, exhibit anisotropy, with sizes along $\langle 111 \rangle$ being approximately twice as large as in the other directions. Therefore, the rough crystallite shape, although not strictly real, would be a spheroid with one axis, parallel to the $\langle 111 \rangle$, being twice as long as the other two. The crystallite sizes of 75 nm and 72 nm agree well with the grain sizes of 73 ± 2 nm and 76 ± 2 nm from SPED-ASTAR, for pristine and irradiated regions, respectively. The major phase, NiCoFe, in ODS-NiCoFe, revealed an increase in microstrain for the irradiated region (0.00037) by 0.00016 (76 % relative increase) compared to the pristine region (0.00021). The relative increase in the microstrain exceeds the error limit of the measurement and thus, indicates the presence of radiation-induced defects, especially dislocations.

4.6. Defect analysis via TEM

To verify the possibility of radiation-induced swelling and understand the microstructural origins of irradiation hardening, we conducted STEM-BF examinations in the irradiated regions of NiCoFe and ODS-NiCoFe, as shown in Fig. 6 (a)–(j). The images contain FIB-induced curtaining effect and fine-sized loops/defect clusters (<10 nm) that

Fig. 5. X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis of ODS-NiCoFe. (a) Normalized XRD patterns illustrating the face-centered cubic crystal structure for pristine and irradiated regions of ODS-NiCoFe (offset to ease the visualization). (b) Zoomed-in XRD patterns overlapped to show broadening for $\{111\}$ peak following irradiation.

Fig. 6. Defect analysis of the irradiated regions of single-crystal NiCoFe and ODS-NiCoFe. (a) STEM bright-field image of the single-crystal NiCoFe with irradiation profile overlaid and FIB-induced loops/defect clusters (Red circles) identified. (b),(c) STEM bright-field images showing dislocation lines/chains (red arrows) and a dislocation loop (blue arrow) in single-crystal NiCoFe from the irradiated region. (d) STEM bright-field image showing oxide nanoprecipitates (yellow arrow) and twin structures (green arrows) in ODS-NiCoFe with irradiation profile overlaid. (e)–(j) STEM bright-field images showing dislocations (red arrows) in Grains 1 to 6, respectively. (k), (l) STEM-LAADF images indicating the interaction of dislocations/defect clusters with a nanoprecipitate (gold arrow) and a grain boundary (black arrow) for ODS-NiCoFe. STEM: Scanning transmission electron microscopy, LAADF: Low-angle annular dark-field.

are homogeneously distributed in the irradiated and pristine regions. The pristine regions (deeper than 1.6 μm from the surface) show the presence of the FIB-induced loops/defect clusters for NiCoFe in Fig. 6 (a) (red circles) and ODS-NiCoFe in Fig. S8 (red circles), which help differentiate Ni^{2+} irradiation-induced defects from FIB-induced defects. We carried out the STEM-BF imaging along $\{110\}$ zone axis for NiCoFe and Grains 1, 2, 3, 5, and 6 (indicated in Fig. 6 (d)) of ODS-NiCoFe and along $\{100\}$ zone axis for Grain 4 of ODS-NiCoFe. The STEM-BF micrographs do not indicate any visible evidence of voids/bubbles for NiCoFe (Fig. 6 (a), (b), and (c)) and ODS-NiCoFe (Fig. 6 (d)–(j)), indicating irradiation-swelling resistance. Fig. S9 illustrates the conventional TEM images of NiCoFe and ODS-NiCoFe for in-focus, over-focus, and under-focus conditions, which also do not indicate the presence of TEM resolvable voids. The STEM-BF images (Fig. 6 (a)–(j)), however, indicate the presence of predominantly dislocation lines/chains (red arrows) and a few dislocation loops (blue arrow) induced by irradiation. Hence, dislocations are the dominant defect structures in the irradiated regions of NiCoFe and ODS-NiCoFe. The dislocation length density and

mean dislocation length calculations are indicated in Table 1 for NiCoFe and Grains 1 to 6 selected within the irradiated region of ODS-NiCoFe. Table 1 demonstrates that the dislocation length densities in the ODS-NiCoFe are slightly larger compared to the single-crystal NiCoFe even though the order of magnitude is the same. The difference includes the

Table 1
Dislocation length density and mean dislocation lengths.

Material	Grain ID	Dislocation length density ($\times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$)	Mean dislocation length (nm)
NiCoFe	–	2.6	249
Single-crystal			
Polycrystalline ODS-NiCoFe	Grain 1	7.7	172
	Grain 2	3.0	83
	Grain 3	4.5	173
	Grain 4	9.6	39
	Grain 5	5.0	157
	Grain 6	0.0	0

discrepancies in the manual calculations of the thickness of each grain using convergent beam electron diffraction patterns. Additionally, dislocation length density calculations could contain human errors while using the line-intercept method due to the varying contrast in the STEM-BF images of the grains. For ODS-NiCoFe, we estimated a volume-averaged dislocation length density of the six grains as $\sim 6.1 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$ and a mean dislocation length of 104 nm. Thus, the average sizes of the dislocations are reduced by $\sim 58\%$ from 249 nm in NiCoFe to 104 nm in ODS-NiCoFe. In addition, as denoted in Fig. 6 (d), the microstructure of ODS-NiCoFe also features nanostructures such as grains with a size of a few nanometers and nanoprecipitates (yellow arrow). Fig. 6 (d) also demonstrate the occurrence of twin boundaries (green arrows), justifying the $\Sigma 3$ grain boundary misorientations observed in Fig. 4 (c) and (d). Furthermore, Fig. 6 (k) and (l) displays the STEM-LAADF images showing the possibility of dislocation pinning at the grain boundary (black arrow) and at a nanoprecipitate (gold arrow).

4.7. Molecular dynamics simulations showing defect evolution mechanisms

Movie S1 (Supplementary Information) illustrates one of the MD irradiation damage overlapping cascade simulations showing the formation and evolution of various defect structures in single-crystal NiCoFe. Fig. 7 (a) shows a snapshot during the formation and evolution of defect structures in the simulations, including different types of dislocation chains and vacancy clusters containing (≥ 3 vacancies), at ~ 0.09 dpa. Similarly, Fig. 7 (b) depicts the same snapshot with various types of dislocation chains and interstitial clusters (≥ 3 interstitials). We rapidly cooled the sample from 580°C to 26.85°C to capture the snapshot. The smaller $1/6 \langle 110 \rangle$ type stair-rod dislocations (represented in pink), indicated by gold arrows in Fig. 7 (a), contain small vacancy clusters (< 10 vacancies). The stair-rod dislocation chains with trapped vacancy clusters can potentially form stacking fault tetrahedrons (SFTs) [11]. The SFTs are the predominant types of vacancy clusters found in various irradiated fcc materials, formed either during collision cascades [11] or through the aggregation of vacancies and vacancy clusters [82]. Except for the stair-rod type dislocations, all other dislocations are interstitial type, indicated by the interstitial clusters (> 4 interstitials) enclosed

within the dislocations. The large and three-dimensional (3D) dislocation chains containing interstitial clusters, as seen in Fig. 7 (a) and (b) (purple arrows in Fig. 7 (b)), predominantly consist of $1/6 \langle 112 \rangle$ type Shockley dislocations along with smaller partials of stair-rod, Hirth, perfect, and other dislocations. Similarly, the smaller $1/3 \langle 111 \rangle$ type Frank dislocation loops also contain interstitial clusters. Thus, the MD simulations for single-crystal NiCoFe divulge various types of dislocations/interstitial clusters and vacancy clusters that form during irradiation damage cascades. Furthermore, Fig. 7 (a) indicates that the vacancy clusters that are not associated with stair-rod dislocations are considerably smaller in size compared to the Shockley dislocation chains containing interstitial clusters. For instance, an eight-vacancy cluster is approximately 0.57 nm in size, while one of the bigger dislocation chains measures 4.6 nm, almost one order of magnitude higher, as shown in Fig. 7 (a). Fig. 7 (c) and (d) demonstrates this size disparity of vacancy and interstitial clusters quantitatively. Fig. 7 (c) presents the distribution of vacancies in various cluster sizes (in terms of the number of vacancies) and Fig. 7 (d) shows a similar distribution of interstitials in various cluster sizes (in terms of the number of interstitials) after 0.09 dpa irradiation. Fig. 7 (c) indicates a preferential occurrence of mono vacancies over clusters with multiple vacancies and Fig. 7 (d) reveals the higher presence of larger interstitial clusters (> 4 interstitials).

Furthermore, Movie S1 reveals the absorption of stair-rod dislocations (with vacancy clusters) by the dislocation chains. Fig. 8 (a) illustrates one of the snapshots showing the absorption of a large vacancy cluster (stair-rod dislocation) by a dislocation chain containing interstitial clusters. To visualize such absorption for smaller vacancy clusters, the single-crystal NiCoFe simulations for three samples are represented in terms of the evolution of interstitials and vacancies, as shown in Movies S3a-c. Fig. 8 (b) represents one of the snapshots illustrating such recombination of smaller interstitial and vacancy clusters (five defects). Movies S3a-c also indicate that the mobility of interstitials is much higher than that of vacancies and the interstitial clusters move in 3D. Movie S1 also denotes the 3D motion and growth of Shockley dislocation chains (mainly containing interstitial clusters), aided by the absorption of perfect and Frank loops and the merging of the chains. In addition, vacancy clusters can also undergo dissociation, as shown in Fig. S10.

Fig. 9 (a) and (b) denote the effect of a grain boundary on the defect

Fig. 7. Molecular dynamics overlapping cascade simulations showing defect structures in single-crystal NiCoFe at ~ 0.09 dpa after rapidly cooling from 580°C to 26.85°C . (a) Distribution of dislocation chains and large vacancy clusters (≥ 3 vacancies). (b) Distribution of dislocation chains and large interstitial clusters. Gold arrows in (a) and purple arrows in (b) indicate stair-rod dislocations and large dislocation chains, respectively. Distribution of defects in clusters of different sizes expressed as the number of defects for single-crystal NiCoFe at ~ 0.09 dpa and 580°C . (c) Vacancy distribution in clusters. (d) Interstitial distribution in clusters.

Fig. 8. Zoomed-in sequential snapshots showing the absorption of vacancy clusters by interstitial clusters indicated by gold arrows. (a) Interstitial and vacancy clusters are contained in dislocations. (b) Interstitial and vacancy clusters are not contained in dislocations. The vacancies are represented in blue, and the interstitials are represented in black.

evolution in NiCoFe. It compares the evolution of dislocation length density, mean dislocation length, and defective atoms (atoms that are not located on the fcc lattice) with increasing dpa at 580 °C in a single-crystal and a simulation box containing $\Sigma 5$ (210) GB for NiCoFe. The $\Sigma 5$ (210) GB with a misorientation of 53.1° was chosen for these simulations as it is one of the peak misorientations observed in uncorrelated misorientation distribution for ODS-NiCoFe, as indicated in Fig. 5 (c) and (d) (in the inset). Fig. 9 (a), (b), and (c) demonstrates that the existence of the GB leads to a reduction in dislocation length density (however, similar orders of magnitude), mean dislocation length, and defective atoms, compared to the single-crystal for irradiation up to

~0.11 dpa. Fig. 9 (c) and Movie S2 (Supplementary Information) explain and validate the GB effects depicted in Fig. 9 (a) and (b), where the absorption of defects, particularly stair-rod dislocations, occurs at the GB in addition to the absorption by the Shockley dislocation chains. Fig. 9 (c) illustrates some snapshots from Movie S2 indicating the absorption of a stair-rod dislocation (with a vacancy cluster) at the GB, designated by black arrows, where the atoms belonging to the GBs were extracted using centrosymmetry analysis. Furthermore, Fig. S11 reveals a similar absorption of a Frank loop at the GB of NiCoFe alloy.

Fig. 9. Molecular dynamics simulations showing defect number evolution with increasing irradiation dose in displacements per atom at 580 °C in a single-crystal and a simulation box containing $\Sigma 5$ (210) grain boundary for NiCoFe. (a) Dislocation length density evolution. (b) Mean dislocation length variation. (c) Evolution of defective atoms (atoms that are not located on the fcc lattice sites). (d) Sequential snapshots from 0.073 dpa to 0.074 dpa (315–320 number of cascades) for bicrystal NiCoFe illustrating the absorption of a stair-rod dislocation containing vacancy cluster by the grain boundary (black arrows). Ni, Co, and Fe atoms are color-coded as blue, red, and green, respectively.

5. Discussion

5.1. Stability of the nanostructures

In the current work, the nanoprecipitate size analysis separates the thermal effects from the combined effects of radiation damage and temperature and demonstrates that the irradiation conditions do not induce/enhance nanoprecipitate growth beyond the thermal effects. Also, the nanoprecipitate size distribution (Fig. 2 (b)) and the average nanoprecipitate size of 6.4 ± 1.7 nm for the pristine region indicate similar or finer precipitate sizes compared to similar unirradiated ODS-NiCoFe alloys in the literature [23,24], suggesting a minimal possibility of precipitate growth due to the thermal effects at 580 °C. Several studies have reported physical instability of precipitates under irradiation leading to an increase/decrease of the precipitate densities and a decrease/increase in average precipitate sizes for several other potential advanced reactor structural materials depending on the irradiation conditions such as dose, dose rate, and temperature [25,83–85]. Ballistic dissolution phenomenon during the irradiation event and various other phenomena driven by defect formation and migration, such as RIS and precipitate nucleation and growth, contribute to precipitate instability [86]. Such phenomena resulting in the evolution of the precipitates are governed by the interplay between the diffusion of defects and atoms and the damage cascade and hence, the precipitate stability/instability is dependent on the irradiation dose and temperature [83,84,87]. For instance, in ODS steels such as bcc Fe-14CrODS and bcc Fe-18CrODS, larger precipitates shrank with the simultaneous growth of smaller particles (inverse Ostwald ripening) following Fe⁺ irradiation up to 4 dpa at 500 °C, whereas coarsening via Ostwald ripening was observed after 150 dpa at 500 °C [84]. In addition, the apparent stability of the ODS particles was observed at 400 °C after irradiation up to 100 dpa [84]. Studies on ODS-Ferritic-Martensitic steels indicate shrinkage in the nano oxide (incoherent) precipitate sizes and an increase in densities with Fe ion and Ni ion irradiations at different dpa levels up to 200 dpa and various temperatures between 300 °C and 700 °C [85,88]. In ODS-CSAs such as the ODS-NiCoCr, a shrinkage of nano oxides was detected with Ni²⁺ irradiation up to a fluence of 5×10^{16} ions/cm² (maximum of 132 dpa) at 580 °C [25]. In advanced bcc ODS steels such as 14 YWT, oxide particle size and density remained unchanged up to 100 dpa of Ni²⁺ irradiation even at 600 °C [89,90]. Literature suggests that for any irradiation conditions, there exists a critical temperature above which the precipitates remain stable [90]. The present research demonstrates the physical stability of the nano oxide precipitates at an irradiation fluence of up to 5×10^{16} ions/cm² (maximum of 103 dpa) at 580 °C (Fig. 2 (d)). This is because the atomic diffusion compensates for the ballistic dissolution caused by damage cascades, indicating that 580 °C is similar to or beyond the critical temperature for the physical stability of the nanoprecipitates. Even though fcc structures were normally considered to be less radiation tolerant than the bcc structures [91,92], the novel fcc ODS-NiCoFe has exhibited stability of nanoprecipitates similar to bcc ODS-steels. The physical stability of nanoprecipitates is key to providing enhanced irradiation damage resistance compared to conventional and existing potential alloys as the stable nano oxide precipitates can act as defect sinks. Furthermore, stable nanoprecipitates stabilize other nanostructures such as the grain boundaries by resisting their movement to avoid grain growth and recrystallization.

Irradiation-induced loss of crystallinity occurred within the nanoprecipitates, as shown in Fig. 3, even though, the precipitates remain physically stable in terms of their distribution. Earlier studies also indicated that the bulk materials of Y–Ti–Oxides undergo amorphization [93,94]. However, in the current study, the nanoprecipitates in the matrix of NiCoFe do not undergo full amorphization, and possibly the amorphization is a local phenomenon. One of the previous studies on SiOC dispersion-strengthened austenitic stainless steel showed that if the precipitates are fully amorphous, the hardening/strengthening effect

is enhanced and the interface disorder can accommodate more irradiation-induced defects [95]. Therefore, the precipitate-induced hardening is not affected significantly in the current research as the precipitates are not fully amorphous. The literature reports that amorphization is triggered by local short-range order around Ti atoms via the rearrangement of Ti cations and O anions due to irradiation-induced antisite defect formation [93]. For instance, in Y₂Ti₂O₇, an antisite defect occurs whenever Ti and Y cations exchange their lattice positions. Specifically in the first shell, at a Ti antisite defect, Ti shifts from the usual lattice position to accommodate local stresses with a coordination of 5 O anions and a reduction in Ti–O bond length [93]. In the current work, the MD simulations also revealed similar findings showing an increase in the number of Ti atoms with coordination below 6 with the increase in the number of cascades, as illustrated in Fig. 3 (j). An earlier study also showed that the disordering sequence involves a transformation of the pyrochlore structure to a defect-fluorite structure before amorphization in Y₂Ti₂O₇ with irradiation [94]. The Ti-enriched regions in Type II precipitates could represent such a transformation and thus, these regions remain crystalline (Fig. 3 (f)–(i)). The loss of crystallinity in the non-Ti-enriched regions may not pose a substantial negative impact in the present scenario in terms of hardening, given the stability of nanoprecipitates with respect to their distribution. Furthermore, the disorder introduced by the loss of crystallinity at the interfaces can enhance the defect sink strength.

In this study, the grain size analysis separates the thermal effects from the combined effects of radiation damage and temperature similar to nanoprecipitate size analysis, and demonstrates that the irradiation conditions do not induce/enhance grain growth beyond the thermal effects. In addition, as shown in Fig. S8, the pristine region of the ODS-NiCoFe alloy contains minimal dislocations to potentially drive grain growth under thermal effects. Previously, various studies reported the instability of grains under high-temperature irradiation leading to grain growth in nanocrystalline materials [86,96,97]. Depending on the stages of grain growth, the governing mechanisms could be disorder-driven or defect-simulated [86,97]. According to the disorder-driven mechanism, in the initial stages of grain growth, if the grains are smaller than the irradiation damage volume (~10 nm), the damage caused by displacement spikes near the grain boundaries (disorder) acts as a driving force leading to the growth of smaller damaged grains into relatively undamaged neighboring bigger grains [97]. The grain growth is rapid during the initial stages since the damage in smaller grains is more likely to occur entirely. However, in the later stages of grain growth once the grain size reaches the damaged volume dimensions, the grain growth becomes slower and the disorder-driven mechanism fails. In this stage, the defect-simulated mechanism activates where the large defect concentration gradients created due to heavy ion irradiation near the grain boundaries cause atomic jumps across the grain boundaries and thus, lead to the movement of grain boundaries [97]. In the present work, even though ODS-NiCoFe consists of nanosized grains, the majority of the grain sizes (Fig. 4 (a) and (b)) are well beyond the irradiation damage volume of ~10 nm; hence, the probability of the occurrence of disorder-driven and defect-simulated mechanisms is minimal. Thus, ODS-NiCoFe shows greater stability of the nanometer-sized grains under Ni²⁺ irradiation up to a fluence of 5×10^{16} ions/cm² at 580 °C while facilitating better irradiation-induced defect absorption at the grain boundaries with a relatively larger grain boundary area compared to coarse-grained counterparts. In addition, radiation-induced recrystallization was also reported in an advanced steel alloy, 1.4970 (15 wt% Cr-15 wt% Ni), which was irradiated in a 20 % cold-drawn condition with 46 MeV Ni⁶⁺ ions to 64 dpa_{NRT} at 848 K. In this case, irradiation-induced defects provided the activation to stabilize and facilitate the growth of pre-formed nuclei for the recrystallization of grains earlier than the thermal activation [98]. The migration of grain boundaries dissolved voids and generated additional vacancies, which further eased the grain boundary migration [98]. However, since annealing followed MA and SPS in the manufacture of ODS-NiCoFe, the

grains were not in a highly damaged state to provide sufficient driving force for the nucleation of recrystallized grains. Moreover, the presence of nanoprecipitates further reinforces the stability of the grains in ODS-NiCoFe, as they pin the movement of grain boundaries. Furthermore, high-temperature (580 °C) irradiation up to $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ does not affect the crystallite size (Table S5) which indicates the physical stability of the crystallites, as the amorphization and growth of the crystallites are undesirable. The crystallite stability under irradiation further validates the grain stability observed via SPED-ASTAR (Fig. 4).

5.2. Irradiation-hardening resistance

Earlier studies demonstrated a hardening of 16 % for single-crystal NiCoFe with similar doses of irradiation up to $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and at a slightly lower temperature of 500 °C [29]. The current study indicates a slightly higher value of 25 %. However, the introduction of grain boundaries and the addition of nanoparticles of Y_2O_3 and Ti did not significantly affect the amount of hardening. Irradiation hardening occurred due to the plastic strain induced by irradiation. Hence, the irradiated region of ODS-NiCoFe exhibited a higher GOS by 0.07° and a higher microstrain by 0.00016 compared to the pristine region, as measured using SPED-ASTAR and XRD, respectively. The GOS parameter obtained by SPED-ASTAR to complement XRD micro-strain values opens a possible discussion forum for further development of such parameters and possibly finding correlations between the GOS, micro-strains obtained from XRD, and dislocation length density calculations. Thus, the current work uniquely explores the use of two indicators, microstrain, and GOS, as measures of plastic strain introduced by irradiation defects. Plastic strain gauges the amount of dislocations in this case, especially because they are the primary defect structures in the irradiated regions of NiCoFe and ODS-NiCoFe, as revealed in TEM observations (Fig. 6) and MD simulations (Figs. 7 and 9). The MD simulations complement the TEM analysis as the Shockley dislocation dominant large 3D dislocation chains with larger interstitial clusters (purple arrows in Fig. 7 (b)) are similar to the large dislocation chains observed in STEM-BF observations shown in Fig. 6 (red arrows). In the literature, it was shown that nucleation of Shockley partial dislocations dominate plasticity at elevated temperatures in NiCoFe alloy via molecular dynamics nanoindentation simulations [99,100]. Thus, irradiation induces dislocations of similar nature comparable to nanoindentation dislocations.

Irradiation hardening can consist of contributions from the source and friction hardening [86]. The source hardening refers to resistance to start the dislocation movement on the glide plane and friction hardening refers to the resistance to dislocation movement caused by the dislocation interactions and obstacles [86]. In the single-crystal NiCoFe sample, source hardening and friction hardening via dislocation interactions contribute to irradiation hardening. For instance, a dislocation loop pinning a dislocation line, as detected in Fig. 6 (c) (blue arrow), imparts additional friction for dislocation motion and thus, contributes to irradiation hardening. However, in the ODS-NiCoFe specimen, friction hardening due to the impediment of dislocation movement at nanoprecipitates and grain boundaries also occurs along with the conventional source and dislocation interaction-induced hardening. Fig. 6 (l) reveals such friction hardening in ODS-NiCoFe where dislocation pinning occurs at a nanoprecipitate (gold arrow) and a GB (black arrow). Such a hardening effect also validates the hardness improvement shown in Fig. 1 (e) due to the enclosure of nanostructures in NiCoFe. Even though additional hardening mechanisms are active in ODS-NiCoFe compared to NiCoFe, ODS-NiCoFe still showed a similar amount of hardening of ~25 %.

The experiments show a slightly higher dislocation length density in ODS-NiCoFe, while MD simulations report a slightly lower density for bicrystal NiCoFe compared to the single-crystal NiCoFe. One possible explanation for this discrepancy is that the MD simulations consider only a single high-angle grain boundary (53.1°), which has a higher sink

strength compared to lower-angle grain boundaries that are more prevalent in real polycrystalline materials and possess lower sink strength. Hence, in a real polycrystalline material, the decrease in dislocation density might not be significant. Also, the dislocations in the order of 1 nm or smaller in size might not be detected in the STEM. Furthermore, as explained in Section 4.6, the dislocation length density calculations based on the STEM images might contain human errors. However, experiments and MD simulations show similar tendencies of reduction in the mean dislocation length. The reduction in the mean dislocation length in the ODS-NiCoFe sample by ~58 % in comparison to the NiCoFe sample, as illustrated in Table 1, explains the effect of defect sinks such as the grain boundaries and the matrix-nanoprecipitate interfaces, which absorb the defects and thus, do not allow the growth of dislocations. Similarly, the MD simulations show a reduction in mean dislocation length, as illustrated in Fig. 9 (b), and a decreased amount of defective atoms, as shown in Fig. 9 (c), due to defect absorption at the GBs shown in the MD simulations (Fig. 9 (d) and Fig. S11). Thus, defect absorption at the sinks compensates for the additional hardening mechanisms in ODS-NiCoFe leading to hardening similar to single-crystal NiCoFe. Similar hardening in NiCoFe and ODS-NiCoFe could also be related to the roughness of the materials. Since the error bars for nanoindentation hardness are relatively high, especially for ODS-NiCoFe, as shown in Fig. 1 (e), a true difference on the order of 3–5 % could be hidden there.

The irradiation hardening observed in ODS-NiCoFe is lower than the hardening observed in some of the ODS steel alloys, such as the 15Cr ODS steel, 14Cr ODS steel, 12Cr Yttria, Zirconia, and Alumina ODS-steel alloys, MA 956, and ODS-Eurofer [75,77,101–107]. Some ODS steel alloys exhibit lower irradiation hardening than ODS-NiCoFe; however, the alloys were measured at reasonably lower doses compared to 103 dpa (at peak) in the current study and varied temperatures, irradiation energies, and pre-irradiation microstructural states [108–111]. For instance, higher Cr-containing alloys such as the 19Cr–4Al, 16Cr–4Al, and Al-free16Cr–0.1Ti ODS alloys showed 11 %, 7 %, and 6 % hardening at 0.8 dpa Ni ion irradiation at -50°C [108]. Similarly, some of the ODS steel alloys exhibited no hardening for a dose of 30 dpa at 550 °C; however, the alloys contain $<0.4\%$ Y_2O_3 and 0.1 % Ti compared to 1.5 % Y_2O_3 and 1.2 % Ti in ODS-NiCoFe [109]. Also, 12Cr-ODS steel demonstrated irradiation hardening of $<15\%$; however, the materials were in a deformed state due to rolling in pre-irradiation conditions and the irradiation dose was up to 15 dpa and temperature up to 300 °C [110,111]. An elaborate survey of irradiation hardening for various ODS-steel alloys is reported in Table S6 (Supplementary Information). Hence, ODS-NiCoFe is uniquely characterized at a higher dose and temperature, compared to all the alloys, and exhibits better irradiation-hardening resistance, compared to various bcc ODS steel alloys and single-crystal NiCoFe.

5.3. Irradiation-swelling resistance

In the case of NiCoFe, literature suggested the occurrence of tiny voids [29,112] at the end of the ion range i.e. at a depth of about $\sim 1.6 \mu\text{m}$ [112] after Ni^{2+} irradiation with 3 MeV energy and up to a fluence of $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ similar to the current work; however at 500 °C [29,112]. Nevertheless, the voids contributed to only less than 0.2 % swelling, and thus, NiCoFe exhibited higher irradiation-swelling resistance compared to other similar CSAs such as NiFe, NiCo, and NiCoCr [29,112]. The current TEM investigations revealed no significant voids in NiCoFe, as shown in Fig. 6 (a)–(c) and Fig. S9, with irradiation up to the same fluence; however, at a slightly higher temperature of 580 °C. This reiterates the higher swelling resistance for NiCoFe reported previously [29,112]. Similarly, the absence of observable voids/bubbles in ODS-NiCoFe (Fig. 6 (d)–(l)) indicates that ODS-NiCoFe possesses irradiation-swelling resistance either similar to or better than NiCoFe.

MD simulations reveal the defect evolution mechanisms that explain the irradiation-swelling resistance of NiCoFe and ODS-NiCoFe, as

indicated in Movies S1, S2, S3a-c, and Figs. 8 and 9. For single-crystal NiCoFe, the simulations demonstrate the absorption of vacancy clusters either in the form of stair-rod dislocations or smaller clusters (Fig. 8) by the interstitial clusters as the major underlying phenomenon for the suppression of void formation. Higher mobility and 3D motion of the interstitial clusters, as shown in Movies S1 and S3a-c, facilitate the absorption. The mobility of interstitials is much higher than that of vacancies, leading to the formation of large interstitial clusters that eventually form dislocations. The 3D migration of interstitial clusters in NiCoFe further facilitates the formation of interstitial-type large dislocation chains and increases the probability of vacancy and interstitial recombination. Previous MD simulations in SP-CSAs such as NiFe also demonstrated 3D migration of interstitial clusters; albeit, the simulations considered only the evolution of interstitials that were not irradiation generated [113]. The current work advances these simulations by considering the concurrent evolution of interstitial and vacancy clusters and more accurately predicts the 3D migration of interstitial clusters via irradiation damage cascades. The 3D migration could be attributed to the atomic size differences and structural distortions in the random solid solution alloys such as NiFe, NiCoFe, NiCoFeCr, and NiCoFeCrMn, which lead to a higher interstitial energy barrier compared to pure metals and dilute solid solution alloys by multiple folds (4–5) [113]. In contrast, the simulations illustrated 1D migration for Ni and NiCo alloys [113]. Hence, the vacancy clusters could not coalesce and grow to form voids of significant size, due to their limited mobility further assisted by the higher mobility and 3D motion of the interstitial clusters. The dissociation of vacancy clusters, as depicted in Fig. S10, also contributes to the suppression of the growth of vacancy clusters and the formation of voids.

Movie S2 and Fig. 9 (c) illustrate the absorption of stair-rod dislocations (with vacancy clusters) at $\Sigma 5$ (210) GB and by Shockley dislocation chains. The absorption of stair-rod dislocations at $\Sigma 5$ (210) and $\Sigma 5$ (310) GBs was also previously observed in nanocrystalline fcc Cu [34]. Such absorption results in fewer vacancy clusters in bicrystal NiCoFe compared to single-crystal NiCoFe, as evident from the lower number of defective atoms for bicrystal NiCoFe (Fig. 9 (c)). Thus, in ODS-NiCoFe high-density GBs, twin boundaries, and nanoprecipitate-matrix interfaces can act as defect sinks [25] and impart additional irradiation-swelling resistance compared to single-crystal NiCoFe. In addition, XRD results show no significant lattice parameter changes in the irradiated region of ODS-NiCoFe, as described in Table S5, indicating the possibility of the occurrence of limited residual vacancies. Thus, the results support the absence of significant voids observed in Fig. 6 (d)–(j) and Fig. S9 (Supplementary Information) for ODS-NiCoFe following irradiation at 580 °C. Some conventional structural alloys demonstrated lattice shrinkage indicating lattice relaxation due to the possible residual vacancies generated by the preferential migration of interstitials to sinks such as dislocation loops, grain boundaries, and interfaces [114,115]. Apart from void swelling, preliminary studies on He-implanted CSAs illustrate that chemical complexity plays a key role in determining He bubble density, size, and He bubble-induced swelling [116,117]. It was found that NiCoFe exhibited an average He-bubble diameter of 4.3 nm and a density of $5.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ nm}^{-3}$, and thus, an overall swelling of $\sim 0.3\%$, following a 200 keV He⁺ implantation up to a fluence of $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ ions/cm}^2$ at 500 °C via TEM and atom probe tomography. These results indicate that the NiCoFe alloy showed better resistance to He-bubble swelling compared to Ni, NiFe, NiCoCr, and Mn-based high-entropy alloys, and was comparable to the Pd-based high-entropy alloy [116]. In another similar TEM study, NiCoFe implanted with 100 keV He⁺ ions up to a fluence of $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ ions/cm}^2$ at 500 °C exhibited higher bubble sizes and lower densities compared to NiCoFeCr and NiCoFeCrMn [117]. Due to the presence of additional defect sinks in ODS-NiCoFe, the He-bubble swelling resistance of ODS-NiCoFe is possibly better than that of the NiCoFe alloy. Thus, polycrystalline ODS-NiCoFe should exhibit better irradiation-swelling resistance than conventional structural alloys and

single-crystal NiCoFe.

5.4. Novelty and outlook

The current work represents one of the first attempts to assess the high-temperature irradiation effects in novel ODS-CSAs, and the first to investigate ODS-NiCoFe. Also, the study uniquely examined ODS-NiCoFe after irradiation to an exceptionally high dose, reaching a peak of 103 dpa. We employed a range of advanced experimental techniques, including SPED-ASTAR, which, to the best of our knowledge, has not been previously applied to irradiation studies, alongside conventional nanoindentation, TEM, and XRD. This research proposes grain orientation spread as a novel parameter for assessing irradiation damage at the grain level, in addition to the conventional micro-strain measured by XRD. The work uniquely quantified dislocations in fine grains (mostly $<1 \mu\text{m}$) using STEM-BF imaging, involving multiple sample tilts to investigate grains along similar zone axes ($\{110\}$), a rarely reported approach. Also, the experimental results correlate well with MD simulations in explaining the mechanisms of irradiation-hardening and -swelling resistance; despite differences in irradiation doses (up to 103 dpa experimentally vs ~ 0.11 dpa in simulations). Such complementary results are uncommon yet indispensable. However, the simulations could not reveal the role of nanoprecipitates as defect sinks due to the unavailability of appropriate interatomic potentials, presenting an opportunity for future work. In addition, quantifying the loss of crystallinity in the nanoprecipitates remains challenging due to their nanoscale size and internal crystallinity variation, warranting further study. While further investigation is needed, the research provides compelling evidence for the high-temperature irradiation tolerance of the novel ODS-NiCoFe alloy.

6. Conclusions

The following conclusions can be summarized based on the characterization of a 3 MeV Ni²⁺ irradiated oxide dispersion strengthened (ODS)-NiCoFe at 580 °C up to a fluence of $5 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (maximum of 103 dpa) and complementary molecular dynamics (MD) simulations.

- The hardness of ODS-NiCoFe with nanosized grains was twofold higher than the softer fcc NiCoFe, increasing from 2.0 ± 0.1 GPa to 4.3 ± 0.9 GPa, and comparable to the harder bcc ODS steel alloys.
- Irradiation hardening remained around 25 % for ODS-NiCoFe, similar to the single-crystal alloy, despite the presence of abundant hardening sources such as oxide nanoprecipitates and grain boundaries, indicating superior irradiation hardening resistance in polycrystalline ODS-NiCoFe compared to single-crystal NiCoFe and several well-known bcc ODS steels.
- Oxide nanoprecipitates remained physically stable, with no significant changes in their average size or density following irradiation. The nanoprecipitate densities were $9.27 \times 10^{22} \text{ m}^{-3}$ and $9.02 \times 10^{22} \text{ m}^{-3}$, and the mean equivalent diameters were 6.7 ± 1.7 nm and 6.4 ± 1.7 nm, for irradiated and pristine regions, respectively. This suggests that ballistic dissolution during irradiation is balanced by atomic diffusion. Two types of oxide nanoprecipitates were observed: Type I (Ti-oxides) and Type II (Ti–Y–Zr oxides). Upon irradiation, the nanoprecipitates exhibited local loss of crystallinity; however, Type II precipitates retained some crystalline regions locally enriched with Ti.
- The average grain size and misorientation distribution remained largely unchanged following irradiation, indicating the physical stability of grains, as their sizes exceed the irradiation damage volumes. The average (geometric mean) grain equivalent diameters were 73 ± 2 nm and 76 ± 2 nm for the pristine and irradiated regions, respectively.
- The average grain orientation spread increased by 0.07° and the microstrain increased by almost two folds i.e., 0.00021 to 0.00037

with irradiation, representing strains caused by irradiation-induced defects.

- No significant lattice parameter changes occurred post-irradiation in ODS-NiCoFe. Similarly, NiCoFe and ODS-NiCoFe showed no observable voids and irradiation-induced dislocations dominated the microstructures.
- Dislocations emerged as the dominant defect structures, with the average dislocation length density rising slightly from $\sim 2.6 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$ to $\sim 6.1 \times 10^{13} \text{ m}^{-2}$, while the mean dislocation length dropped from 249 nm to 104 nm, compared to single-crystal NiCoFe. MD simulations divulge defect evolution mechanisms such as the absorption of vacancy clusters including the stair-rod dislocations with trapped vacancy clusters at grain boundaries and Shockley dislocation chains. The absorption is assisted by the three-dimensional migration of mobile interstitial clusters including dislocation chains, thus; validating void swelling resistance in polycrystalline ODS-NiCoFe.

Hence, our work deems ODS-NiCoFe alloy as one of the better radiation-tolerant materials, especially for high-temperature irradiation effects. Hence, the current research needs to be further continued to establish the irradiation resistance of ODS-NiCoFe. Concentrated solution alloys (CSAs) such as medium-entropy alloys, composed of multiple transition metals, have a complex chemical structure. Moreover, the strategy of embedded nanostructures in such CSAs can be combined with the recent development and understanding of defect dynamics and radiation effects. Thus, the results can pave the path for further investigations and eventual qualification of materials for advanced nuclear reactor applications.

Data availability

The data will be made available upon a reasonable request.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmrt.2025.07.079>.

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